

"DESCRIPTION OF WOMEN'S SPIRIT IN ZULFIYA'S POEMS"

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Abstract: This article provides information about the image and experiences of the female psyche in the poetry of the poetess Zulfiya. Poem collections, which are the indelible treasures of the poet's life notebook, were analyzed, and the images, experiences and thoughts of the creator were thoroughly studied. In Zulfiya's poetry, a woman appears not only as a symbol of motherhood, but also as a hardworking, courageous and strong person. In the analysis, the poet's poems depict women as brave, tenacious, selfless people, both during the war and in peacetime. As a singer of loyalty and devotion, her poems dedicated to her husband are also covered meaningfully and comparatively. When every reader reads Zulfiya's lyrics, one can clearly feel the feelings of longing for her husband.

Keywords: Poetry, the scope of the topic, poems, feeling, poetry, lyrics, loyalty, loyalty, courage, experiences, longing, love for the homeland, emotion.

Zulfiya (Zulfiya Isroilova) was born on March 1, 1915 in Tashkent, into the family of an Isroil blacksmith. She first studied at a secondary school, then at a girls' school. She began her creative career very early, working for many years in journalism and publishing. She is the author of many poetic works and translations. She is the wife of the famous Uzbek poet Hamid Olimjon. The breath of Hamid Olimjon's poetry is always clearly felt in her work. No matter what topic the poetess touches, you can always feel her feminine spirit and devotion.

Men o'tgan umrga...

Hayot kitobimni bexos varaqlab,

Men o'tgan umrga achinmay qo'ydim.

Tabassum o'rnida kuldim charaqlab.

Suyish kerak bo'lsa - telbacha suydim.

Kiyganim ipakmi, chitmi yo kimxob,
Yurak boyligidan qilmabman parvo.
Meni og‘ushlagan hayot naq oftob,
Yangi qo‘shiq talab unda har saboq.

In this poem, the poetess summarizes her life, looks back at the life path she has traveled, compares her life to a book, and is grateful for her life. Because throughout her life, she did not betray her faith, did not betray her conscience, and remained faithful to her pure heart. Through this poem, she invites every reader to summarize her life and laugh at it. The poetess was able to see life in bright colors: she smiled brightly where she needed to smile, and loved when she needed to love like crazy...

When World War II began, Zulfiya, among her friends, followed her father, son, brother, and beloved husband to the front in the first months of the war, and began to create a lyrical image of Uzbek women who worked day and night in their place. In the poet's poem "Hijron", written in the fall of 1942, we can see the image of a young bride who did not lose her hopes and dreams during the bitter moments of hijron:

... Yorim, sevar yorim jo‘nadi jangga,
Mening yuragimga tushdi hijron-dog‘.
Men sevgan dildorning sevgan yurti bor,
Ishq doim erk uchun hijronga rozi.
Bu hijron mangumas, visoli ham bor –
Qahraton qishlarning bo‘lganday yozi.

The poetess' poems, which are included in the collections "Hayot jilosi", "Arik gullaganda", "Hayollar", "Sog'inish" and others, which were created in memory of the poet Hamid Olimjon, belong to the category of poems imbued with feelings and philosophical generalizations, imbued with the spirit of love for life. Also, the theme of respect for women and love for mothers has a special place in the work of the poetess Zulfiya. Zulfiya repeatedly addressed this theme in different periods of her work. As a result, the poetess' poems such as "Ona", "Ona ko'ksi", "Mening yoruba onaginam", "Ona ko'ksi" were created. There are many lyrical experiences in the

poetess' work that reveal the love of mother and child, the inner and outer image of femininity.

MENING MEHRIBON ONAGINAM

Onam, mening mushfiq, mehribon onam,
Qalbimda ovozing, o'zing qayerda?
Quyosh og'ushiga solganmi olam,
Shuladay odiming qaysi asrda?
Qaysi mintaqada nafasing hayot,
Qayda kim yo'liga ko'zing muntazir!
Qaysi sayyorada ey, sen Odamzod,
Farzanding bo'shliqni etmoqda asir.¹

In the poem "My Loving Mother," the poetess clearly conveys her spirit and thoughts. In the very first lines of the poem, Zulfiya says that her mother's voice is in her heart, but she is searching for it. She compares her life to those of her ancestors, questioning the centuries. She even turns to regions and planets, searching for her mother's breath. The poetess uses her words in such a way that we can clearly understand her talent and spirit from the following verse:

Qay qabila, qay chol, qay cho'qqi, qay g'or
Sening ilk shodliging shohidi makon.
Olam tug'ilishi sen ilk bor,
Farzand-la sukunatni uyg'otgan zamon.

Through these lines, the poetess says that the world was created by a mother who shared the silence of the earth with her child. Zulfiya describes a woman not only as the support of the family, but also as a symbol of the entire nation and the Motherland. She shows a woman as a symbol of national culture, the Motherland and the people. For example, in the poem "Mother-Motherland", the poetess combines the symbols of a woman and the Motherland, writing:

Sen – yurtim, sen – onam, mehri to'la,

¹ Zulfiya. Bahor keldi seni so'roqlab. – Toshkent: Yangi asr avlodi, 2019. - 10 b.

Bag‘ringda ulg‘aydim, shodman, Ona!

In this poem, mother and homeland are described as one whole, and their love is the most important factor in human life. In addition, Zulfiya describes motherhood in harmony with nature. In her poems, comparisons of mother to the sun, spring, and trees are often found. Through these images, the poet emphasizes the sacredness of motherhood, like nature. At first glance, it seems that spring, longing, and loyalty are at the top of her work, but the comparison of mother to the homeland also leads in her work. Our poem above is a clear example of this.

Ko‘rganmiding ko‘zlarimda yosh

Sog‘inganda izlab bir nishon,

Qabring tomon olar edim yo‘l.

Keltirarding menga bir zamon,

Endi har chog‘ men eltaman gul.

Keldim. Uzoq qoldim men sokin,

Sening aziz boshingda yolg‘iz,

Osmon tiniq edi va lekin,

Parcha bulut yetib keldi tez.

Ko‘kda mening boshimda turib,

Go‘yo yuragimda qalqdi u.²

This poem by the poetess “Have you seen tears in my eyes” is read smoothly and fluently in one breath. From the first lines of the poem, the reader understands that this poem is dedicated to Hamid Olimjon. Therefore, the poetess describes her experiences and feminine feelings in a simple language that is understandable to the reader, without exaggerating. In particular, this is the case in the poem above. She says that when she misses her beloved, she turns to the grave of the creator, and if earlier Hamid Olimjon brought flowers to the poet every night, now Zulfiya also brings flowers to her husband’s grave every time. She also writes that during Hamid Olimjon’s life, the sky was always clear, and after he left the world, the clouds in the creator’s head gradually began to break apart, and as a result, her heart soared.

² Zulfiya. Bahor keldi seni so‘roqlab. – Toshkent: Yangi asr avlodi, 2019. - 68 b.

In conclusion, we can say that Zulfiya's lyrics are poetry born of deep thought and passionate feelings. The poet's lyrical hero is often perceived as a person of high intellect. He is somewhat pensive, sometimes philosophical, and sometimes serious and touching. In the poet's spiritual and spiritual searches, in the process of creating a poetic image, the landscape of emotions, the tension of experiences, acute dramatic situations and collisions are emphasized.

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